

METHODS OF USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *in this article, information about the types of modern technologies and their importance in learning a foreign language is provided. Each person can learn to use the benefits of modern technologies.*

Key words: *modern technologies, methods, electronic resource, individual section, language system, language proficiency, academic disciplines.*

Modern education, including its foreign language component, creates new challenges, which are reflected in the current-generation Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Education. The presiding idea of the standard is to form and develop universal and executive competences and professional culture of a specialist of the future ready to address provocation and problems using one's acquired knowledge, abilities and skills, professional values and empirical experience. The goal of the research under review may be described as a strive to present a technology of creating electronic teaching materials by liberal arts undergraduate students of teacher coaching institutions. The prime aim of this paper is to contemplate the specifics of generating electronic educational resources to be used in face-to-face and distance FL learning. Goal-oriented interaction of educational process is one of the aspects conducive to enhancing the features of FL teaching. Teaching techniques in cooperation are implemented in the course of the performance of game charges by the

students in the situations of society extended to them. For mastering a language, significant condition is communication in the target language. According to our observations, learning in cooperation is learning in the process of communication of students with each other, and purposeful work in cooperation can expand interest in classes and significantly increase the time of speech practice of each student in the lesson.

Computer training. This is teaching a foreign language using curricula designed for working with a computer. It arose on the ideas of programmed teaching and current days, has a significant impact on all aspects of the educational process in connection with the enormous computerization of secondary and inflated schools, the creation of computer programs for different academic disciplines, including for those studying foreign languages, using the capabilities of the Internet. Nowadays, the following types of computer training programs have become widespread: those devoted to mastering individual sections of the language system, the development of speech skills, control programs assessing the degree of language potentiality, socio-cultural programs introducing the culture of the country of the target language. At the same time, in the programs of recent years, multimedia systems that synthesize sound, video and text have been increasingly used, which allows using all types and means of visualization within the framework of a computer training course with maximum efficiency. Thanks to the use of the EER program, the probabilities of online open-source tasks (creative tasks) are most fully realized. Contemporary technologies are considered an active agent for enhancing the quality of the educational activity and a vital pre-condition for developing modern teacher non-manual competency. All types of training materials (online courses, video lectures, training devices, tests, polls, interactivities) used to build a particular course are concentrated in one ISpring Suite program. A significant feature is the add-in over Microsoft Office (Power Point), which is a time-saver, allowing the consumer not to waste time getting used to the interface. A new modern approach to the application of new technological processes and new modern methods of teaching in the educational process. The purpose of foreign language teaching is not only to educate students and

develop certain, speaking skills, but also to develop students' abilities. development, increasing interest in the foreign language they are learning, using the internal capacity of their memory, and building students' confidence in their own power. As you know, the educational process is complicated. Foreign language lessons include the stages of developing relevant speaking skills and competencies through the presentation of new learning material, its practice through a variety of exercises, and its application to a variety of speech situations. A number of interactive methods can be used to increase student engagement in the classroom. The term correlative method is derived from the English word "interactive", which means to increase students' internal activity. There are a number of types of this method, some of which are currently widely used interactive methods such as "brainstorming", "business games", "pinboard", "cluster", "sinkveyn", "cubic technology", role-playing games are aimed at increasing the activity of students in the educational process. In interactive teaching, group teaching, small groups of 3-5 people are effective. So that, it can be called "Innovative technology". Innovative technologies are ways to develop the acquisition of knowledge through the operate of factors that increase the effectiveness of education, the design and implementation of different pedagogical processes. Its main purpose is to make innovations and swap in the activities of teachers and students in the educational summons which requires the use of interactive methods. Interactive methods are based on the active, free and independent thinking of each learner involved in the learning process. When using these methods, learning becomes a fun activity.

In conclusion, learning a foreign language using computer programs and other modern technologies can be more effective and motivating. These modern technologies also help the development of types of that writing, speaking, listening and reading. This can lead to excellent results in English language learning.

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